

OUT-OF-BAND ISOLATION OF RF FILTERS

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ABSTRACT

Experimental and theoretical analyses have been conducted on coaxial, stripline, and microstrip filters to evaluate their capability of preventing undesired microwaves from entering systems. Three approaches allow the observed isolation to be described: detailed circuit modeling, finite attenuation of waveguide below cutoff of the filter enclosure, and, above cutoff, a statistical correlation observed between the median isolation and the enclosure perimeter.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing numbers of rf emitters, combined with the higher sensitivity of receivers, contribute to the increased vulnerability of systems to out-of-band rf. Filters are the most practical cure for excluding these interference signals, but they are less than perfect in their out-of-band rejection.

Experiments have been conducted on lumped element, semi-lumped element, stepped impedance, series gap, coupled line, and interdigital filters using a conventional network analyzer. Theoretical analyses have been conducted allowing the observed results to be extended to structures other than those tested, as well as to shunt stub, comb-line, waveguide, and fin-line filter structures.

The out-of-band filter rejection we have observed can be described by using (1) detailed circuit modeling, (2) attenuation of waveguide below cutoff for the housing of the filter,

and (3) a statistical observation for higher frequencies where the housing is no longer below cutoff, in which the median isolation is observed to correlate with the inverse of the perimeter of the housing.

Figure 1. Center conductor pattern of coupled-stripline band pass filter.

DETAILED CIRCUIT MODELING

Detailed circuit modeling was carried out for the structures tested using TOUCHSTONE, a computer code for microwave circuit analysis. A typical band-pass filter using coupled lines is shown in figure 1. Only the center strips of the stripline are shown. These conductors are sandwiched between two dielectric boards with metal on the outsides. The small circles are screws or eyelets to suppress radiation between input and output. They define a waveguide below cutoff at lower frequencies.

The model used on the computer is shown in figure 2. Each coupled section is modeled by a quarter-wave coupled line section (directional coupler), and the parasitic capacitances of the ends of each line are carefully represented. The computed response is shown in figure 3 compared to the experimental data. The model is very close to the measured data up to 5.5 GHz. Other factors limit the isolation above that frequency unless the response of the filter has a lower insertion loss than those other factors. For example, we see a close match between the model and the data around 11 GHz.

Figure 2. Touchstone Model of coupled-line filter of fig. 1.

WAVEGUIDE BELOW CUTOFF

A waveguide has a cutoff frequency below which it is commonly considered not to propagate any power. However, it continues to propagate power, but at a high attenuation. This attenuation is well controlled and is used as the basis for making baseband precision attenuators. The attenuation is a function of structure and independent of frequency.

A waveguide must be effectively a half-wavelength or wider to propagate in its lowest order mode, the TE₁₀ mode. The printed metal pattern of a stripline filter in figure 1 is located in the H-plane of a structure looking like a waveguide, where it does not interfere with waveguide propagation. When a filter is in the rejection band, it has a very high VSWR at each end and is fairly efficient at launching waveguide modes. The attenuation of a waveguide below cutoff is 27.4 dB/square; that is, if the waveguide is 1 in. wide it will give 27.4 dB/in.

The waveguide defined by the rivets in figure 1 is about 3 squares long from input conductor to output conductor and therefore should give about 82-dB isolation up to the cutoff frequency. The cutoff frequency is calculated to be 7.1 GHz. Note from figure 3 that the maximum isolation varies about 80 dB up to 7 GHz. Since the eyelets are not a perfect wall, the effective width is a little wider than the distance between their centers. Oscillations in the isolation are due to varying efficiency of mode launching at the ends.

Figure 3. Comparison of measured and computed isolation for the filter of fig. 1.

RANDOM ISOLATION ABOVE WAVEGUIDE CUTOFF

Above the cutoff frequency there is no simple theory that dictates what the isolation will be. But it has been observed that filters with a small perimeter in their cross section have more isolation than filters with a larger perimeter. The isolation of a sample of filters has been plotted statistically over the bands in which waveguide-mode propagation dominates (7 to 11 GHz for the aforementioned filter). An example of the statistical distribution is given in figure 4. It is a representation of the probability that the isolation will be less than the isolation specified, over the band of interest. The filters were all straight with the connectors on the ends. Taking into account the length of the filter did not further tighten up the correlation. The median isolation is the 50% point on each curve.

Figure 4. Statistical (Cumulative Distribution) representation of isolation of a sample of filters above cutoff of their enclosures.

When these medians are plotted against the perimeter of the filter enclosure, a consistent pattern is revealed, as shown in figure 5. Making the perimeter smaller by a factor of 10 increased the isolation in decibels by a factor of 4.

Figure 5. Median filter isolations vs. enclosure perimeters.

CONCLUSIONS

To obtain high isolation from filters out of band, the structure should be modeled in detail with first order parasitics (those for which you can account) to assure that the isolation is high enough. The filter should be built in a enclosure that gives the desired isolation as a waveguide below cutoff. And the perimeter of the cross section should be kept small enough to provide the desired isolation. It should be feasible to build filters with high out-of-band isolation with proper attention given to these design parameters.